

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Will be dark or light brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not all the time black in coloration. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear may be found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. However, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 feet in length. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, however their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are some of one of the best at climbing timber. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb bushes for protection, food, and even hibernation. The vast majority of their diet is [teddy bear big teddy bear](#) vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food plan: Their varied food regimen gives them the flexibility to dwell in a large range of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They are the more than likely bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per 12 months. Although their conservation status is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and decreased habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the guidelines, which led to the name of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals comparable to elk and moose. Their shade varies from mild blonde to dark brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet lengthy, and have a shoulder peak of 3. Three feet. □□ Diet: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been recognized to prey on large mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than these found within the Rocky Mountains as a consequence of a richer weight loss plan. Every year there are 46 attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Recognized for his or her aggressive conduct, grizzlies are liable for the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are solely discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Dimension: Kodiak bears are nearly as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1, four hundred pounds, 8 ft lengthy, and four ft tall at the shoulder. □□ Food regimen: Their diet is much like mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, resulting from more plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a more advanced social structure which results in much less battle between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears may be aggressive. Because of their isolation, there is only one assault on people each other yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is generally made up of meat, often from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and could be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species due to loss of habitat from climate change. Despite their monumental size polar bears will be quick, sustaining a 6 mph pace in the water. □□ Options: In comparison with different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, narrow head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight loss program consists mostly of animals, particularly seals which they'll odor from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears could be extraordinarily dangerous. They see humans as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon as a result of remote nature of their habitat. Known for its cream shade chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Simple to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered susceptible. □□ Measurement: One of the smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses,

fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on people are growing as people encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Dangerous? They are one among the best bears to tame (and therefore common in circuses), however Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered only in China. 99% of its weight loss plan is bamboo. Actually, the second individual in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while protecting his sheep. Known for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. ☐☐ Location: Pandas are found solely in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they are considered a susceptible species. ☐☐ Size: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and may be over 4 toes tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It also has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in mild brown and white. ☐☐ Food plan: Not like different bears the panda's weight loss plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Options: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo retains them regular: they poop over 40 times a day! ☐☐ Dangerous? Attacks are uncommon but dangerous, provided that pandas have one of the very best chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐ Location: The Solar bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its population is uncertain however thought of weak and on the decline as a result of loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and other physique elements used in conventional medicines. ☐☐ Size: They stand only 39 to 55 inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Options: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that appears like a rising sun. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Weight loss plan: Sun bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In truth, they have an extremely long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Harmful? As a consequence of its shy nature, assaults are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐ Location: The Sloth bear is found in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of lower than 20,000, they are considered vulnerable. ☐☐ Measurement: They're fifty five to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they are easy to inform other than different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very quick and may out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the other way up from bushes. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. ☐☐ Weight-reduction plan: Their weight-reduction plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Harmful? They're one of the crucial aggressive bears, with the most assaults on humans, principally because of surprise encounters. They blow the dust round with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine nicely with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's final quick-faced bear. The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that seem like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. ☐☐ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last brief-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. ☐☐ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Weight-reduction plan: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a weight-reduction plan consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Dangerous? Dwelling in distant mountains, these shy bears may be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, but have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA tests were unable to determine what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas should not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in area. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or defending their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their very own family which can be closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR

SURROUNDINGS. Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that may point out a bear is close by, during which case you need to be further vigilant. Listed here are a number of suggestions you need to use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't by accident startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you might have nice intentions, a bear is more likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP).** If you happen to see a bear, don't attempt to approach or feed it. This contains meals, but additionally your toiletries, for instance. Whichever method you select, make certain it is at the least 200 ft away out of your tent so you don't entice bears to your campsite. 4. **Keep CALM.** In the event you meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make your self look as large as possible, waving your arms above your head. You may as well lengthen a jacket above your head to make yourself look bigger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Battle Again.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, do not play dead. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.Zero to 8.Four toes long, and 4.Zero to 5.25 ft tall, the largest bear by both dimension and weight is the polar bear. The biggest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all your energy and hope that it will again down. Which bear is probably the most harmful? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for essentially the most assaults. When in bear country, it's always sensible to hold bear spray. It's effectively deserved, particularly when cubs are round. Each year there are roughly forty six grizzly assaults, 6 resulting in loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome reputation. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most likely to see an American black bear, on average there is only one assault per year. When it comes to raw chunk power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's bite reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When utilizing the bite drive quotient (bite power relative to size), the sun bear packs probably the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the hearth however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he grew to become an icon and to today is the star of the longest-running public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has impressed numerous through-hikers to try to master the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a duty-free life-style. He also might be the primary bear to obtain his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada close to where he was from. Chris additionally wrote Tips on how to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal parts backpacking food and ultralight gear. After through-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and how-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

